

Supplementary table 3. CS indications stratified by parity (nullipara vs. multipara)

Supplementary table 3 Ten most reported indications by birth outcome and parity of 29,640 babies born by CS of a sample of 105,872 births (multiple indications possible)

	Antepartum stillbirths		Intrapartum stillbirths		Live births	
	Nullipara	Multipara	Nullipara	Multipara	Nullipara	Multipara
1	Fetal death (40.7%)	Fetal death (32.4%)	Prolonged labor (27.4%)	Previous CS (26.5%)	Prolonged labor (36.3%)	Previous CS (54.2%)
2	Prolonged labor (16.0%)	Previous CS (30.7%)	Fetal distress (17.3%)	APH (20.9%)	Fetal distress (20.7%)	Prolonged labor (20.2%)
3	HT disorders (16.0%)	APH (14.5%)	HT disorders (17.3%)	Prolonged labor (14.3%)	HT disorders (12.8%)	Fetal distress (10.8%)
4	Malpresentation (13.6%)	Prolonged labor (14.1%)	APH (12.3%)	Fetal death (10.5%)	Malpresentation (8.2%)	Elective CS (4.2%)
5	APH (13.6%)	HT disorders (12.0%)	Previous CS (11.1%)	Fetal distress (9.6%)	Elective CS (7.8%)	HT disorders (6.8%)
6	Fetal distress (11.1%)	Malpresentation (12.0%)	Fetal death (9.5%)	Malpresentation (9.6%)	Multiple pregnancy (3.7%)	Malpresentation (7.9%)
7	Multiple pregnancy (6.2%)	Multiple pregnancy (8.3%)	Malpresentation (5.6%)	HT disorders (8.7%)	PROM (2.1%)	Multiple pregnancy (6.3%)
8	Elective CS (3.7%)	Elective CS (3.7%)	Multiple pregnancy (2.8%)	PROM (5.7%)	Post-term (1.9%)	APH (3.1%)
9	PROM (1.2%)	Fetal distress (1.2%)	PROM (2.8%)	Cord complication (4.9%)	APH (1.5%)	PROM (2.5%)
10	Cord complication (1.2%)	PROM (1.2%)	Cord complication (2.8%)	Multiple pregnancy (3.2%)	Cord complication (0.8%)	Post-term (2.1%)

APH: Antepartum haemorrhage; HT disorders: hypertensive disorders; PROM: premature rupture of membranes